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Women employed with advanced degrees globally

Increased by 25.26% between 2014 and 2022

The indicator "Females employed with advanced degrees" measures the percentage of employed women who possess an advanced degree, such as a master's, doctorate, or an equivalent professional qualification. This indicator reflects the higher education level among employed women and can provide insights into the degree of specialization and qualification of the female workforce. It is used to analyze the labor market, assess the effectiveness of educational policies, measure progress towards gender equity, and help companies understand the availability of highly qualified female talent. A high percentage indicates good access for women to higher education and a work environment that values such qualifications, while a low percentage may signal barriers to accessing advanced education or recognition of these qualifications in the labor market.

Women employed with advanced degrees globally in 2022. Data analysis on the percentage of employed women with advanced degrees in 2022 reveals significant differences among countries. Israel and Ukraine lead the ranking with percentages close to 100%, followed by Lithuania, Ireland, and Australia with percentages over 90%. These data indicate a strong presence of highly qualified women in the labor market of these countries, probably reflecting effective educational policies, a favorable work environment, and recognition of the value of advanced skills. Specifically, Israel, with 100%, shows perfect representation of women with advanced degrees among the employed, suggesting a highly inclusive educational system and a labor market that rewards advanced qualifications. Ukraine, with 99.8%, indicates a similar situation despite the political and economic difficulties the country is facing. In Western Europe, countries like Belgium, Sweden, and Norway also maintain high percentages, reflecting progressive societies with a long tradition of promoting gender equality and access to education. The United States, with 92.6%, demonstrates the importance of women in the qualified labor market, although gender gaps in other areas of work and society persist. Asia is represented by Singapore and Japan in this high range, with Singapore boasting a percentage of 92.8%, demonstrating the effectiveness of its inclusive educational and labor market policies. In Central and Eastern Europe, countries like Estonia, Latvia, and Russia show percentages between 87% and 90%, suggesting good access to higher education for women, although there may be cultural or economic barriers further limiting this representation. Poland and Hungary show slightly lower percentages, around 60-70%, highlighting the need to improve inclusion policies and promote advanced education for women. In Latin America, the data shows a mixed picture. Countries like Argentina and Brazil have percentages around 50%, suggesting a good level of participation of women with advanced degrees in the labor market, but with ample room for improvement. Chile and Colombia show lower percentages, around 40%, indicating potential barriers both in access to higher education and recognition of qualifications in the labor market. Africa and South Asia generally present very low percentages. Countries like Nigeria, Pakistan, and India show percentages below

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10%, with India at 8.4%. These data highlight significant structural and cultural challenges that limit women's access to higher education and the qualified labor market. Barriers may include gender discrimination, lack of adequate educational infrastructure, poverty, and restrictive social norms. In the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) region, the data is particularly concerning. Countries like Saudi Arabia, Kuwait, and Morocco show a percentage of 0%, indicating that women with advanced degrees are not represented in the labor market. This could reflect deep gender inequalities, legal and cultural restrictions preventing women from accessing and using their education in the work context. The situation in sub-Saharan Africa is equally critical. Countries like Ethiopia, Burundi, and Mali show percentages below 1%, with Tanzania at 0.9%. These data reveal the enormous challenges these nations face in providing access to higher education for women and creating a labor market that recognizes and values such qualifications. In summary, the data analysis shows a clear division between high-income and low-income countries regarding the percentage of women with advanced degrees in the labor market. In more developed countries, inclusive policies and robust educational systems have led to greater participation of highly qualified women. However, even in these countries, there are persistent challenges related to full gender equality in work and society. In developing and less developed countries, structural, economic, and cultural barriers continue to significantly limit women's access to higher education and the qualified labor market. These data underline the need for targeted and sustainable interventions to improve gender equality in education and work globally. Policies should focus on scholarship programs, incentives for female education, creating inclusive work environments, and removing cultural and legal barriers that prevent women from realizing their full professional potential. Only through a global and coordinated commitment will it be possible to close the gap and ensure that all women, regardless of their country of origin, have the opportunity to contribute fully to economic and social progress.

Women employed with advanced degrees globally between 2014 and 2022. Data analysis on the percentage of employed women with advanced degrees between 2014 and 2022 reveals significant trends and substantial variations among countries. Some countries show impressive progress, while others have seen marked decline or even a total absence of women with such qualifications in the labor market. Let's start with the countries that recorded the highest percentage increase. Algeria, for example, saw a remarkable increase in the percentage of women with advanced degrees, rising from 12.9% in 2014 to 26.5% in 2022, with an absolute variation of 13.6 percentage points and a growth rate of 105.43%. This significant progress can be attributed to improvements in educational policies and women's access to higher education, as well as greater acceptance and integration of women into the labor market. Similarly, Austria doubled its percentage, rising from 30.4% to 62%, with an absolute variation of 31.6 points and a growth rate of 103.95%. These data suggest a strong commitment by the country to promoting advanced education among women and ensuring them job opportunities corresponding to their qualifications. Botswana and Brazil also showed significant progress, almost doubling their initial percentages. Botswana went from 27% to 54.2%, while Brazil saw an increase from 24.5% to 47.5%. These increases indicate an improvement in educational and labor opportunities for women in these nations. Indonesia, with an 88.70% increase, and Mongolia, with a 74.07% increase, follow the same positive trend, although starting from initially different percentages. Moving to Europe, Slovakia, Malta, and Portugal showed significant improvements. Slovakia went from 35% to 60.7%, Malta from 36% to 56.8%, and Portugal from 44% to 69.6%. These data suggest that European countries are making important strides in promoting higher education for women and recognizing their value in the labor market. Slovenia and Luxembourg, with initially high percentages, continued to improve, with Slovenia reaching 84.7% and Luxembourg 86.6%. Despite these progress, some countries have seen very limited growth or even a decline in the percentage of employed women with advanced degrees. Costa Rica, for example, saw a slight

decrease from 38.8% to 38.4%, while countries like Chile, Ecuador, and Madagascar recorded more significant decreases, respectively of 6.06%, 6.51%, and 8.96%. These declines may indicate economic difficulties, changes in educational or labor policies, or other factors that have prevented women from obtaining or maintaining job positions corresponding to their advanced qualifications. Countries like the Russian Federation and Belarus show even more dramatic declines. Russia went from 97.3% to 87.6%, while Belarus saw a massive decrease from 100% to 67.6%. Armenia and Sri Lanka also recorded significant declines, with decreases of 32.68% and 48.88%, respectively. These data suggest that, despite an initially high level of advanced education among women, there have been recent developments that have drastically reduced their job opportunities in these countries. The most drastic decline was observed in countries like Ethiopia and Saudi Arabia, where the percentage of women with advanced degrees has practically disappeared. Ethiopia went from 17.7% to a meager 0.7%, while Saudi Arabia dropped from 12.8% to zero. Uganda followed a similar path, dropping from 7.9% to zero. These data are alarming and indicate severe structural problems preventing women not only from accessing advanced education but also from participating in the labor market in a meaningful way.

Conclusions. The number of women employed with high degrees increased on average from 43 units to 53.9 units, equivalent to a 25.26% variation between 2014 and 2022. There are countries where the number of women employed with high degrees has increased significantly, such as Algeria with +105.43%, Austria with +103.95%, Botswana with +100.74%, Brazil with +93.88%, and Indonesia with +88.70%. There are countries where the number of women employed with high degrees has significantly decreased, such as Sri Lanka with -48.88%, Tanzania with -52.63%, Ethiopia with -96.05%, Saudi Arabia, and Uganda with -100.00%. Considering the 2022 data, we can notice that generally in countries with medium to high per capita incomes, the value of women employed with high degrees is above 40%.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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